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Teaching the art of communication through drawing

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ABSTRACT

Engineering drawing is a form of communication. Sketching skills are vital for communicating ideas, and understanding of the principles behind drawing conventions is needed to ensure clear communication between designers and fabricators. However, students are losing that ability to communicate as universities move towards CAD-only courses. What is needed is a course that reflects the real-world relationship between drawing, sketching and CAD: the modern engineer sketches an idea, takes it into 3D CAD, then produces 2D manufacturing drawings where necessary.

An exercise was designed in order to teach sketching and CAD skills to first-year engineering students at The University of Sheffield in an industrially relevant context, with the focus on communication rather than conventions. Students were given novel 3D-printed shapes and asked to sketch the part using standard drawing conventions so that someone else could reconstruct it.

Each student then created a CAD model from someone else's sketch, providing written feedback, and produced manufacturing drawings using SolidWorks.

The method described in this paper has been shown to be an effective and relevant way for students to learn the principles of engineering drawing, sketching and CAD. Peer feedback was shown to be an effective learning tool for both parties.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering skills, Curriculum development

Keywords: graphics, CAD, peer feedback

INTRODUCTION

"The single biggest problem in communication is the illusion that it has taken place." [1] Engineering drawing is a form of communication. Manufacturing drawings communicate a designer's intent to the fabricator. When an engineer wants to communicate an idea to another engineer, the first thing they reach for is a pencil. It

has also been suggested that sketching is a way of offloading the visio-spatial working memory [2], allowing more space for design thinking. It is thus an integral part of the design process. Despite this, mechanical engineering programmes are increasingly moving away from hand drawing and teach little sketching [3,4]. Students are also coming to university with poorer hand drawing skills and performing poorly in drawing courses that do exist [5]. Communication has been identified as something students in group design projects struggle with, because of a lack of common “design language” and “communicative tools” such as sketching [3]. Stacey et al. noted that while “freehand sketches are a fast and powerful medium for expressing design ideas... misinterpretation of sketches is a major cause of communication failure in design teams” [6]. For this reason, teaching of hand drawing skills cannot and should not be entirely replaced by CAD-only courses.

The emphasis in traditional drawing classes has been on adherence to strict conventions such as line widths, text height and hatching types. As engineering programmes move away from teaching hand drawing to focus on drawing interpretation [7] and CAD skills, even with the introduction of modern interactive teaching tools [8,9], the key concepts for drawing identified by academics and industry experts [10] still focused around particular conventions such as orthographic projection, how to section, dimension and annotate. While these conventions are undoubtedly useful in forming a clear common language, it is important that the emphasis is placed on the communication itself rather than the conventions. With the advent of CAD and the rapid pace of technological development, engineers must understand the fundamental principles behind the conventions in order to be able to use them flexibly across different media and in interdisciplinary contexts. Otherwise, they are likely to discard conventions altogether and fall into ambiguous communication.

Both the traditional method and the CAD-only method fail to reflect the real-world relationship between drawing, sketching and CAD. Traditional courses tend to start with pencil drawing on drawing boards, with sketching and CAD introduced later, once “the foundations” have been laid down. The modern engineer sketches an idea, takes it into 3D CAD, then produces 2D manufacturing drawings where necessary. In this paper, it is argued that drawing and CAD teaching should reflect this process more accurately, rather than being taught in isolation, and should emphasise the development of communication skills. A prototype exercise is detailed and analysed.

1 BACKGROUND

In September 2016, the first cohort of a new MEng Engineering programme began their studies at The University of Sheffield. The programme was intended to be interdisciplinary, covering mechanical, civil, electrical and electronic, and chemical and biological engineering amongst others. This represented an opportunity to look again at the teaching of engineering drawing and computer-aided design (CAD). Through discussions with the relevant teaching staff across the faculty, it became clear that the main requirements common to all disciplines were for students to be able to sketch, to understand the relevant drawing conventions, and to be able to use CAD.

In the Mechanical Engineering department, the teaching had previously consisted of a series of lectures accompanied by hand drawing exercises, and a separate CAD course. This reflects historical engineering practice, where draftsmen would produce

manufacturing drawings by hand (or later in 2D CAD) and engineers might separately produce 3D CAD models for use in Finite Element Analysis.

However, modern design and manufacturing tools, and the widespread availability of prototyping tools such as 3D printing mean that the modern engineer approaches the design-manufacture process very differently (see Figure 1). After an initial (sketched) concept, products may be directly designed within CAD, the idea taking shape as they are drawn; in civil engineering, the model may be created in Building Information Modelling (BIM) software so that it links with other design information; and crucially, parts can in some cases be manufactured directly from 3D models, bypassing the 'drawing for manufacture' process altogether. Where they are used, manufacturing drawings tend to be produced in CAD packages from the 3D model, and are increasingly used purely as a reference against which to evaluate the finished article, rather than the instructions on how to produce it. The use of templates for both drawing sheets and drafting standards has reduced the need for engineers to commit to memory entire drafting standards, allowing a focus on the fundamental elements.

Fig. 1. Comparison of traditional and modern design processes

2 DESIGN OF LEARNING AND TEACHING ACTIVITIES

In order to more accurately reflect the interplay of sketching, CAD, and manufacturing drawings, and the importance of communication above the recall and application of specific drafting standards, an exercise was designed for 35 first-year engineering students at The University of Sheffield. By the end of the exercise, the students were expected to be able to:

- Communicate engineering concepts through sketching
- Use accepted drafting conventions to describe an object geometrically
- Interpret an engineering sketch and reproduce the object in CAD
- Produce part and assembly drawings in CAD
- Select and correctly mark appropriate tolerances for a hole and shaft based on a specified fit type

Each student was randomly assigned a 3D-printed part from a range of nine, consisting of three mating pairs and a three-part assembly. The parts are shown in Figure 2. Including physical interaction with machine parts in drawing classes has been trialled elsewhere [5, 11] and was found to improve students' spatial awareness and engagement. Each of the parts was a novel shape drawn in SolidWorks® using a combination of simple and complex operations. The use of novel shapes rather than existing components was intended to remove the ability of students to recognise the object and thus fill in missing information from memory. This simulates real-world conditions where a novel component is being designed.

Fig. 2. CAD models of parts used in the exercise

Students were allowed to take the part away and told not to show it to anyone, but to sketch the part using standard drawing conventions and fully dimension it, using notes to clarify where necessary, so that someone else could reconstruct it. Students had previously attended a lecture and practical class where instruction on drawing conventions was given and students had an opportunity to practise sketching and receive feedback.

The students' sketches were collected and redistributed at random to those with a corresponding mating part. After some CAD tuition, they were asked to create a 3D model from the sketch and provide written feedback to the sketcher, focussing on whether the information had been communicated clearly. At this point, they were allowed to discuss the model with their partner and receive clarity on points of confusion. They were then asked to modify their model in light of the discussion and share the finished part with their partner.

Although some efforts have been made to integrate the teaching of hand drawing and CAD at other universities [5], this approach goes further, linking the two parts in a single exercise via an interpretation task that forces students to consider the viewpoint of those to whom they must communicate, and teaches the value of clarity and a common language in the form of conventions.

After further teaching on drawing for manufacture and basic tolerancing, they were each asked to produce manufacturing drawings of the two mating parts using SolidWorks, including an assembly drawing with a Bill of Materials. They were also given a fit for the mating hole and shaft (based on descriptions in [12] e.g. "loose

running fit”), and asked to add appropriate tolerances to the relevant dimensions on the part drawings.

3 ASSESSMENT

Students were asked to electronically submit a portfolio containing their sketch, feedback on their partner’s sketch, CAD models before and after discussion, and part and assembly drawings. The marking scheme is shown in Table 1. It can be seen that clarity and completeness feature prominently, and less weighting is given to adherence to specific conventions.

Table 1. Marking scheme for the exercise

Task	Weighting (%)
Sketch	15
<i>How well does it convey the necessary information about the part?</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity • Completeness • Use of space • Proportion • Correct use of conventions (orthographic/isometric, sectioning, centre lines, dimensions etc.) 	5 5 1 1 3
First model	15
<i>How well does it represent the information in the sketch?</i>	
Feedback	10
<i>Does it identify all the issues with the part (clarity, completeness, use of space, proportion, etc.)?</i>	
Second model	20
<i>How closely does it replicate the part?</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic features (extrude, revolve etc.) • Holes (location, countersinking etc.) • Complex features (loft/sweep etc.) 	10 5 5
Detail drawings (each)	15
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completeness (no. of views, hidden detail, full dimensioning) • Clarity (details not overlapping etc.) • Correct tolerancing of hole/shaft mate • Use of space (sensible scaling) • Title block 	6 2 5 1 1
Assembly drawing	10
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of space • Clarity • Balloons • Correct BOM • Title Block 	2 2 2 3 1

4 RESULTS

By the end of the course, most students were able to demonstrate an ability to communicate clearly and an understanding of basic engineering drawing concepts. Examples of original sketches and final CAD drawings are shown in Figures 3 and 4, along with the feedback provided by another student on the sketch.

Fig. 3. (a) Original sketch with main errors shown; (b) final CAD drawing

Excerpts from the student feedback provided on the sketch (Fig. 3a):

“The sketch made the shape of the object clear... however whilst drawing I couldn't place the smaller details (the protrusions and holes) on the object due to a lack of centre lines and dimensions stating where on the object they should be. I had to guess where the holes went... Hidden lines would have helped identify how far the holes go into the shape along with their respective dimensions... Dimensions were sometimes ambiguous as some were similar and didn't have projection lines.”

Excerpts from the student feedback provided on the sketch (Fig. 4a):

“... showed a clear understanding of how to... clearly convey how the object would look in real life... a good use of different types of lines to represent the interior detail... some confusion with the scale... and I had to estimate the distance of the innermost indents at the bottom of the shape... some issues with reading the measurements [which are not] connected directly to the ends of each part... some measurements were not provided... I would recommend double checking whether the dimensions at the top of the front-on view add up, labelling centre lines and the height of the cylinders on top of the shape as well as the distance between them, and including the dimensions of width of the removed square on the front view... rather than on the view from above... isometric view would be desirable, however it is not essential as the overall shape was clear. The information provided about [thread] proved to be especially helpful.”

Fig. 4. (a) Original sketch with main errors shown; (b) final CAD drawing

It is clear from the improvement in clarity and completeness from the sketches to the final drawings (leaving aside the obvious advantages given by using CAD), that most students had achieved the intended learning objectives. The quality of feedback provided also shows that through the experience of using the sketches to create a CAD model, most students grasped the salient points of what makes a good engineering drawing and why clear communication matters when specifying for manufacture.

5 EVALUATION

This exercise reflects real-world use of CAD and drawing, and places the emphasis on developing the “communicative tools” and common “design language” [3] that students are missing. The use of sketching allowed them to focus on correctly using drawing conventions to communicate, rather than on drawing neatly or with the correct pencil. These skills should be transferrable to other standards (such as civil, chemical, or electrical drawing) since students understand the purpose of drawing rather than just memorising rules. The process of interpreting and feeding back on the sketches also gave the students the opportunity to understand the impact of good and poor practice on the effectiveness of communication, and to reflect on their own submission. The use of 3D-printed parts allowed the students to relate their drawings to a physical object, while also giving the flexibility to create complex, novel geometry that could not be replicated by traditional methods.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The method described in this paper has been shown to be an effective way for students to learn the principles of engineering drawing, sketching and CAD in an industrially relevant context. Peer feedback was shown to be an effective learning tool for both parties.

In the next iteration of the exercise, students could print parts from their models to be able to compare visually with the originals and understand how differences arose, which would be a useful form of feedback. Alternatively, augmented reality facilities at the University may be used to allow students to visualise the model in 3D and compare that way. This will additionally broaden the students' understanding of the uses of CAD modelling and increase engagement with the exercise.

The cohort used for this exercise was much smaller than those of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering to whom such courses have previously been delivered. In order to roll out this exercise to those students, a peer review method for marking will be trialled.

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